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1 **Metabolomics and traditional indicators unveil stress of a seagrass (*Cymodocea nodosa*)**
2 **meadow at intermediate distance from a fish farm**

3

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19

20 **Abstract**

21 Seasonal variation of structural, physiological and growth indicators and the metabolome of
22 the seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa*, as well as biogeochemical conditions of underlying sediment
23 were studied in two meadows growing at increasing distance downstream from a fish farm in
24 the Aegean Sea in order to assess seagrass performance under stress. Horizontal rhizome
25 production decreased significantly with proximity to the fish farm (0.67 and 1.57 g DW m⁻² d⁻¹)

26 ¹ close and far from the fish-farm, respectively). This coincided with observed effects on
27 ecophysiological indicators, such as rhizome nitrogen, leaf carbon and leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, which were
28 elevated with proximity to the fish-farm. Seasonality was shown by some indicators being
29 elevated in either in the warm (C of all tissues and leaf $\delta^{34}\text{S}$) or the cold period (N of all tissues).
30 Growth promoting metabolites (sucrose, fructose, myo-inositol, heptacosane, tetracosane,
31 stigmasterol, catechin and alpha-tocopherol) were lower close to the zone, whereas metabolites
32 involved with stress-response (alanine, serine, proline, putrescine, ornithine, 3,4-
33 dihydroxybenzoic acid and cinnamic acid) were higher. We found that growth-promoting
34 metabolites were positively correlated with horizontal rhizome production, whereas the
35 metabolites related to stress were negatively correlated. Metabolomic fingerprinting of
36 seagrass provides opportunities for early detection of environmental degradation in marine
37 ecological studies.

38

39 Key-words: Mediterranean; early warning indicators; coastal management; eutrophication;
40 omics; seagrass

41

42

43 Introduction

44 Seagrasses are indicators of environmental deterioration, as meadow declines often point to
45 disturbances that affect the entire ecosystem (Orth et al., 2006). ‘Critical slowing down’ or
46 mortality events show that meadows have reached a tipping point, after which there is low
47 capacity for recovery (El-Hacen et al., 2018). Environmental stress plays the biggest part in
48 plant growth and development (Steinberg, 2011) and therefore stress needs to be identified far
49 earlier to avoid permanent loss of seagrasses. Many different indicators are used to evaluate
50 seagrass health in Europe, with little overlap between regions, creating difficulty in making
51 continent-wide assessments (Marbà et al., 2013). Traditional ecological indicators involve
52 nutrient availability in water and sediment (Fourqurean et al., 1992; van Katwijk et al., 2011),
53 structural variables like shoot density and biomass (Agawin et al., 1996; Ibarra-Obando et al.,
54 2004), physiological variables such as elemental and isotopic composition of seagrass tissue
55 (Christianen et al., 2012; M Pérez et al., 1991), and growth such as rhizome production (Duarte
56 et al., 1994), all of which have been identified as good indicators of seagrass stress (Roca et al.
57 2016). The response time of traditional indicators is varied, with physiological indicators
58 generally responding far more rapidly (leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ = ~8 weeks, leaf N = ~2-15 weeks), than
59 structural (shoot density = ~5-25 weeks, above ground biomass = ~10-50 weeks) or growth
60 indicators (leaf growth = ~2-20 weeks) (Roca et al., 2016).

61 Omics tools promise earlier and more targeted detection of stress (Malandrakis et al., 2017a),
62 as they have the potential to reveal how seagrasses respond to abiotic stress, and how tolerance
63 is obtained (Exadactylos, 2015), which could contribute to seagrass management and
64 conservation (Macreadie et al., 2014). Since the turn of the century, and the genome sequencing
65 of the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana* (The Arabidopsis Genome Initiative, 2000), these tools
66 have helped gain a deeper understanding into the molecular function of plants. Among omics,
67 the metabolome provides the best indication of the physical composition of the biological

68 system in question (Horgan et al., 2009). Metabolomics involves detecting and measuring small
69 molecules (<10 kDa), called metabolites, produced by cells during their lifetime (Fiehn, 2002).
70 Due to their position as the end product of gene transcription, changes in metabolites are
71 amplified compared to changes in the transcriptome or proteome (Urbanczyk-Wochniak et al.,
72 2003). Hereby allowing earlier detection of changes in complex biological systems (Peng et
73 al., 2015), making it an accurate tool to determine abiotic stress in plants (Jorge et al., 2016).
74 For instance, plants biosynthesize specialized metabolites, such as the amino acids alanine and
75 proline, in order to cope with environmental stress when stress response genes are expressed
76 (Nakabayashi & Saito, 2015). Low levels of non-structural carbohydrates like soluble sugars
77 can also be precise indicators of environmental stress in plants (Jiang et al., 2013).
78 The observable traits of plants (e.g. biomass, growth rate, etc.) can be greatly influenced by
79 resistance and stress response metabolites (Bino et al., 2004). Combining metabolomics with
80 traditional indicators provides advantages for ecological monitoring. While traditional
81 indicators deliver information on physiological state, environmental quality, and structural
82 growth (Roca et al., 2016), the metabolome compliments these by presenting the chemical
83 response of the plant (Nakabayashi & Saito, 2015), providing a holistic impression of the
84 biological system. Metabolites change in response to environmental stimuli (Malandrakis et
85 al., 2017a), and have cascading effects on indicators such as growth rate (Meyer et al., 2007),
86 therefore exploring these relationships provides information on how changes in the
87 metabolome are projected into changes in the measurable traits of a plant. Nevertheless,
88 understanding of the molecular biology of seagrasses is very limited compared to what is
89 known about terrestrial plants (Davey et al., 2016) and research into seagrass metabolomics is
90 in its infancy (Kumar et al., 2016). Until now, there are only a few studies addressing the
91 response of seagrass metabolites to environmental changes, which suggested that
92 metabolomics was a useful tool in the early detection of *Zostera marina* stress previously

93 unidentifiable (Hasler-Sheetal et al., 2016, 2015). Once more information is gathered
94 concerning stress-response, seagrasses can become even better bioindicators of marine
95 ecosystem health (Malandrakis et al., 2017a), in particular by integrating them into traditional
96 ecological monitoring programs (Kletou et al., 2018).

97 The seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa* forms meadows throughout the Mediterranean Sea and into
98 the Atlantic. It is abundant in the Aegean Sea, where it grows in coastal waters up to 40 m
99 depth (Borum & Greve, 2004). It is the most common species in shallow protected to semi-
100 exposed sub-tidal environments (Orlando-Bonaca et al., 2016). *C. nodosa* is regarded as the
101 most adaptable Mediterranean seagrass (Boudouresque et al., 2009), being more tolerant of
102 nutrient enrichment (Delgado et al., 1997), heat fluctuations (Malandrakis et al., 2017b; Tutar
103 et al., 2017), salinity stress (Piro et al., 2015), and general environmental stress (Garrido et al.,
104 2013). *C. nodosa* is a suitable bioindicator species to assess anthropogenic stress in the marine
105 environment as tissue-based metrics such as nitrogen content in the leaves can be used to
106 distinguish meadows under stress (Papathanasiou et al., 2016).

107 Limited work has been carried out on the impact of fish farming on *C. nodosa*, however, in one
108 study *C. nodosa* showed degraded growth and mortality 100 m from a fish-farm (Delgado et
109 al., 1997). There are no guidelines in place to protect *C. nodosa* from fish farming, unlike the
110 other Mediterranean seagrass species *Posidonia oceanica* which has narrow protections, such
111 as the 400 m safety buffer recommendation between fish-cages and seagrass beds (Holmer et
112 al., 2008). When factoring in current velocities, the intermediate distances are also impacted
113 by fish-farming (Tsagaraki et al., 2013). There are several studies showing that the greatest
114 effects of fish-farming on the suspended sections of the water column in the Mediterranean are
115 between 100-500 m from the fish cages depending on current velocity (Sarà et al., 2006; Sarà,
116 2007; Tsagaraki et al., 2013). Intermediate impacts on the seagrass *P. oceanica* at distances 35-

117 400 m from fish-cages have caused vertical growth declines of 20-40 % of the pre-disturbed
118 values (Marbà et al., 2006).

119 In this paper we assess the performance of *C. nodosa* meadows at intermediate distance from
120 a fish farm using traditional seagrass-based indicators and metabolomics. We do so by
121 quantifying the seasonal variability in nutrient availability in water, pore water and sediment,
122 along with structural (density and biomass), physiological (elemental and isotopic composition
123 of carbon, nitrogen and sulfur) and growth indicators (rhizome production) and the metabolome
124 of seagrasses growing at intermediate distance and away from a fish farm in the Aegean Sea
125 (Greece). We also explore the relationships of *C. nodosa* metabolites of stress and growth with
126 horizontal production, to examine if *C. nodosa* has obstructed performance. The combination
127 of traditional ecological indicators and metabolomics provides more understanding of how
128 environmental stressors affect seagrass stress response. This is the first work to combine
129 traditional seagrass-based indicators and metabolomics to reveal stress of seagrass meadows.

130

131 **Materials and Methods**

132 Sampling Strategy

133 Sampling was carried out at Vourlias Bay (Peloponnese, Greece), which is an allocated
134 aquaculture zone with intense fish-farming activity (9 farms). The site was located
135 approximately 2 km east of the main bay, separated by a headland where there is a fish-farm
136 with 28 cages (37° 27' 08" N 23° 04' 20" E) (Fig. 1). Apart from this aquaculture facility, there
137 were no other features (e.g. rivers, towns) that could cause a disturbance to the environment.
138 Two sampling stations were selected which will henceforth be referred to as 'Station A' and
139 'Station B' at 440 m and 780 m distance from the fish-farm, respectively. The seagrass meadow
140 at Station A was the closest we could find to the fish-farm. Phosphorous sedimentation in
141 seagrass meadows of the Mediterranean, which has been proved a reliable indicator of fish-
142 farm waste, has been shown to decrease exponentially with distance from the cages and the
143 sedimentation rates were roughly 100% and 40% higher at 250 m and 500 m from the fish-
144 farm, respectively, than at non-impacted sites (Holmer et al., 2008). Yet, seagrass meadows
145 growing 800 m downstream from fish farms have shown no evidence of impact (Marbà et al.,
146 2006). Based on the above, it could be expected that there is an effect at 440 m (Station A) and
147 that this effect should be low at Station B, and therefore we can expect to detect differences
148 between stations. The predominant coastal currents in the area move from the North-West,
149 travelling through Vourlias Bay and towards our sample sites, passing the adjacent fish farm.
150 Station A is situated in a small bay where the currents circulate, whereas the currents pass
151 Station B and move down the coast to the South-East (data taken from model described in
152 Tsagaraki et al., 2011).

153 The site was visited twice, during a warm (June 2017) and a cold (March 2018) period, when
154 water temperature was 29° C and 15° C respectively. The water depth was 8 m at both stations.

155 At each station we randomly collected 3 replicates (100 mL each) of bottom water using acid-
156 washed plastic syringes, just above the seagrass canopy. Pore water samples (60 mL each, 3
157 replicates per station) were also collected by acid-washed plastic syringe with a perforated
158 sipper which extracted water from the sediment down to 10 cm depth.

159 Bottom and pore water samples were filtered using pre-combusted filters (Whatman GF/F).
160 Bottom water (25 ml) and pore water (900 μ l) samples were fixed with 10 mL of 10 mM and
161 100 μ l of 100 mM zinc acetate, respectively, and kept frozen for the determination of isotopic
162 composition ^{34}S of sulfate. The remaining filtered water and pore water were kept frozen, and
163 later analyzed for ammonium and phosphate. The filters were kept frozen for the determination
164 of particulate organic carbon and particulate total nitrogen.

165 Sediment samples (4 replicates, i.d. 4.5 cm) were collected by divers using Plexiglas cores,
166 which were randomly inserted in the sediment down to 10 cm depth. Subsamples were taken
167 from three of the replicates, and promptly fixed using 1 M zinc acetate and kept frozen at -20
168 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, to prevent degradation for the determination of the ^{34}S sulfide isotopic ratio. The remaining
169 sediment was also frozen and later used for analysis on total organic carbon (TOC), total
170 inorganic carbon (IC), total nitrogen (TN), ^{13}C and ^{15}N . The fourth sediment sample replicate
171 was frozen and subsequently analyzed for granulometry.

172 Samples for measuring *C. nodosa* density, biomass, elemental and isotopic content, and
173 metabolomics were collected using an aluminium cylindrical corer of area 177 cm^2 . At each
174 station, 5 replicates were randomly taken. When out of the water, these samples were
175 immediately processed to avoid stress to the plants, in order to ensure an accurate metabolic
176 profile. At each station we also randomly hand-collected an additional 6-10 long (40 cm)
177 horizontal *C. nodosa* ramets for analysis of yearly horizontal rhizome production. Seagrass
178 core samples were washed in seawater to remove sediment, and the number of shoots (apical
179 and vertical) were counted for shoot density. The two youngest leaves, rhizomes and root

180 bundles from each of the 5 replicates were rinsed using milliQ water and scraped free from
181 epiphytes before they were put in liquid nitrogen and later stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, to be analysed for
182 metabolites and nutrient content. The remaining seagrass tissue was kept frozen.

183 Laboratory Analysis

184 Ammonium analysis of water samples was carried out using the indophenol blue method
185 (Ivancic & Degobbis, 1984) and determination of phosphate was carried out as described by
186 Strickland and Parsons (1972). Samples for measuring $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{sulfate}}$ were treated by being boiled
187 in acid before sulphate precipitation with BaCl_2 resulting in BaSO_4 . Particulate organic carbon
188 (POC) and particulate organic nitrogen (PON) were measured from the frozen filters. The
189 filtrate was analysed using an elemental analyser according to the Hedges & Stern (1984)
190 procedure.

191 Sediment was dried at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 48 hours to attain density, water content and porosity
192 measurements. The dried sediment was pulverised before being measured for elemental and
193 isotopic composition. Total carbon, nitrogen and ^{15}N were analysed in sediment as it was. The
194 sediment was then acidified for the determination of organic carbon (OC) and ^{13}C . The
195 inorganic carbon (IC) was estimated as the difference between total carbon and OC. The
196 elemental and isotopic composition was expressed in % and δ unit notation (‰ deviations from
197 the established international standards ratio), respectively.

198 For sediment ^{34}S sulfide measurements we used the two-step distillation method (Fossing and
199 Jorgensen, 1989) to obtain the chromium reducible sulfur (CRS) and acid volatile sulfur (AVS)
200 fractions. A 5-10 g fraction of homogenised sediment was combined with 10 mL 50% ethanol
201 in a reaction flask, and degassed with N_2 for 10 minutes. The AVS fraction was attained by
202 distilling the mixture for 30 minutes at room temperature with 8 mL 12M HCl. The CRS
203 fraction required reduction using 1M Cr_2^{+} in 0.5M HCl, and then boiling and distilling for 30
204 minutes. The sulfide extract was collected as Ag_2S precipitate in traps and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ was analysed

205 as described below. Granulometry assessment of the sediment was carried out by removing all
206 grains larger than 63 μm (sand) by wet sieving. The remaining sediment was then categorised
207 using a Sedigraph (Micromeritics 5100) into < 63 μm (silt) and > 0.1 μm (clay).

208 The young seagrass tissue was freeze-dried to be analyzed for total sulfur (TS) and the $\delta^{34}\text{S}$
209 isotopic fraction and their metabolic profile. The remaining (leaves, rhizomes and roots) tissue,
210 which had not been quenched in liquid nitrogen, was dried at 60 °C for 48 hours and
211 homogenized with the young tissue to determine dry weight. Young and remaining tissue were
212 ground to a powder to be used for analysis of elemental and isotopic composition on total
213 carbon (TC), nitrogen (TN), $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ using elemental analyser combustion
214 continuous flow isotope ratio mass spectroscopy. The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ measurement required the ground
215 up seagrass tissue to be weighed into tin capsules along with vanadium pentoxide.

216 Metabolites were extracted, analysed and annotated as described in Hasler-Sheetal et al 2016.
217 In brief, we extracted metabolites from freeze-dried seagrass tissue and analysed by GC-qtof-
218 MS after derivatisation. The data was inspected, annotated and analysed using MassHunter and
219 Mass Profiler Professional (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA).

220 Yearly horizontal production rates were determined through the measurement of the horizontal
221 internodal lengths (the length between leaf scars) on the horizontal ramets (Duarte et al., 1994),
222 in order to determine the leaf plastochrome interval (PI). All ramets were dried at 60 °C for 48
223 hours. The measurements were performed on a Zeiss model Discovery.V12 stereo microscope
224 with a Jenoptik ProgRes® C14 plus camera addition and the aid of ProgRes® CapturePro
225 image capture software.

226

227 Calculations

228 Horizontal rhizome production ($\text{g DW m}^{-2} \text{y}^{-1}$) was calculated from the measured rhizome
229 internodal lengths. First a 30% running average was applied to the data, in order to account for

230 short-term variability (Duarte et al., 1994; Mishra et al., 2018), and then the distances between
 231 consecutive minima recorded, this estimates the annual horizontal growth. The sequence of
 232 internodal length along the horizontal rhizome was measured according to Duarte et al. (1994),
 233 which allowed an estimation of annual horizontal rhizome elongation rate per apex. The
 234 following formula was then applied to the data:

235

236 *Horizontal rhizome production =*

$$237 \frac{\text{annual production} \times \text{horizontal weight} \times \text{apex density}}{\text{horizontal length}}$$

238

239 Where annual production (cm y^{-1}) is each annual cycle measured from the consecutive minima,
 240 horizontal weight (g) is the total dry horizontal rhizome weight of the ramet, apex density (m^{-2})
 241 ²) is the number of apical shoots per metre, and horizontal length (cm) is the total length of the
 242 ramet. We display here the mean production measurements of the two sampling campaigns.

243 Biomass (g DW m^{-2}) was estimated as the dry weight of the seagrass tissue; leaves, rhizomes
 244 or roots, divided by the sampled area. Shoot density (shoots m^{-2}) was estimated as the number
 245 of shoots divided by the sampled area. Biomass and density measurements of the three seagrass
 246 tissues were obtained by multiplying the measured value by the surface area of the aluminium
 247 cylindrical corer.

248 The percentage of sulfur in seagrass leaves, rhizomes and roots taken up from sediment sulfide
 249 (F_{sulfide}) was calculated using the equation:

250

$$251 F_{\text{sulfide}} = \left(\frac{\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{tissue}} - \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{sulfate}}}{\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{sulfide}} - \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{sulfate}}} \right) \times 100$$

252

253 In this formula $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{tissue}}$ is the measured $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ in the leaf, rhizome or root, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{sulfate}}$ in the water,
254 and $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{sulfide}}$ content of the sediment (Holmer & Kendrick, 2013).

255

256

257 Statistical analyses

258 Before statistical testing, we carried out normality and homogeneity checks in SPSS (IBM
259 Corp., 2017) which included using Cochran's Q test. Two-way Analysis of Variance
260 (ANOVA) in SPSS was used to test for differences between stations and seasons. Principal
261 component analyses (PCA) were carried out using the R 'stats' package (R Core Team, 2013)
262 and MetaboAnalyst 4.0 (Chong et al., 2018) in order to identify differences between stations
263 or seasons. Missing values in the metabolomics dataset were calculated using a K-nearest
264 neighbour algorithm, variables with over 50% missing values were discarded. Data was
265 normalised by median, log transformed, and auto-scaled (mean-centred and divided by the
266 standard deviation of each variable). The most influential metabolites in separating the seasons
267 and stations along the principal components (PC) were identified by inspecting the loadings
268 for each PC. Heatmaps were used to visualise how stress and growth-related metabolites
269 differed between stations. Linear regression analysis was carried out on the F_{sulfide} data in order
270 to identify sulfide intrusion and also in order to detect possible relationships between
271 metabolites and growth. Correlations were carried out using Spearman's rho to assess whether
272 stress and growth associated metabolites showed positive or negative trends with horizontal
273 rhizome production. The statistical significance of these correlations were tested using one-
274 tailed and two-tailed t-tests. As it was possible to predict the trend direction in advance, using
275 one-tailed t-testing was appropriate. As two-tailed t-tests protect against type-I errors and
276 cognitive biases, we also report it.

277

278 **Results**

279

280 Pore water ammonium and sediment CRS pools and TN were elevated by 78%, 73% and 170%,
281 respectively, at Station A compared to Station B (Table 1). The other measured biogeochemical
282 variables (bottom and pore water PO₄ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$, bottom water NH₄, POC and PN, and sediment
283 OC, IC, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ sulfide pools) were not affected by station, except for sediment $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and
284 AVS pools, but this depended on season. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signal was highest during the warm period, and
285 AVS pools had an interaction effect between station and season, where the biggest variation
286 between stations was during the cold period. The other values reached significantly higher
287 values during either the warm (pore water PO₄, sediment OC, TN, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$) or the cold period
288 (bottom water PO₄, sediment IC and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, Table 1). The sediment grain size distribution was
289 similar at the two sites (Station A = 91% sand, 9% silt and clay; Station B = 93% sand, 7% silt
290 and clay).

291 Horizontal rhizome production and root biomass were decreased two-fold at Station A
292 compared to Station B (Table 2). Rhizome biomass had an interaction effect between station
293 and season, with the biggest variation between seasons at Station A, twice as high in the warm
294 period. The majority of the structural variables were enhanced during the warm period (shoot
295 density by 83 %, leaf biomass by 218 %, total biomass by 113 % and above:below ground
296 biomass ratio by 100, Table 2).

297 The majority of the measured elemental concentrations and isotopic values were significantly
298 elevated at Station A compared to Station B: Leaf C by 1.5 %, rhizome N by 27 %, root N by
299 37 %, rhizome S by 9.2 %, root S by 30 %, leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ by 11 %, rhizome $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ by 2.4 %, root
300 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ by 1.3 %, leaf $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ by 0.9 %, root $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ by 2.8% (Table 2). Some variables (S of leaves
301 and rhizomes, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of all tissues, and rhizome $\delta^{34}\text{S}$) also had a station effect, but this depended
302 on the season (Table 2). Seasonality was shown by many of the variables being elevated either

303 in the warm (C of all tissues and leaf $\delta^{34}\text{S}$) or the cold period (N of all tissues, Table 2). F_{sulfide}
304 did not show significant differences between stations or sampling periods. F_{sulfide} linear
305 regressions of leaves and rhizomes ($R^2 = 0.58$, $p < 0.01$) and of rhizomes and roots ($R^2 = 0.39$,
306 $p < 0.05$) were positively related indicating sulfide intrusion in the plants from the roots.

307 PCA analysis on metabolite levels in *C. nodosa* leaves revealed clear separations between
308 stations but not seasons (Fig. 2). Metabolites in rhizome tissue showed a seasonal difference,
309 and root metabolites separated mainly by season. However, there was also separation between
310 Station A and B during the winter.

311 Mass spectrometry detected 203 leaf metabolites. A portion of them were related to seagrass
312 stress or growth and varied between stations (Fig. 3). Analysis of the *C. nodosa* metabolome
313 was carried out on leaves and roots. Particular focus was given to the leaves as this is the most
314 active metabolic tissue in plants which has shown the biggest changes in metabolite
315 composition in response to abiotic stress (Obata et al., 2015). Growth and stress-related
316 metabolites varied between stations (Fig. 3, Table 3). Growth-promoting metabolites including
317 sugars and sterols were lower at Station A. The growth metabolite with the largest difference
318 between stations was fructose (2.5 times lower at Station A). Several stress-indicating
319 metabolites including some amino acids were higher at Station A, and two metabolites known
320 to decrease during abiotic stress (2-oxoglutaric acid and stearic acid) were lower at Station A
321 (Fig. 3). Remarkably putrescine was 112 times higher at Station A. Spearman correlations
322 between horizontal rhizome production and growth-promoting metabolite levels in the leaves
323 yielded positive correlations (Table 4), the strongest significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation being with
324 the sugar myo-inositol ($r_s = 0.647$). Spearman correlations between horizontal rhizome
325 production and stress-indicating metabolites yielded significant negative correlations except
326 for 2-oxoglutaric acid, which showed a positive correlation. The strongest correlation was with
327 putrescine ($r_s = -0.624$, Table 4). Linear regression analysis showed a significant negative

328 relationship between horizontal rhizome production and alanine, and a significant positive
329 relationship between horizontal rhizome production and sucrose (Fig. 4).

330 Of the 20 most significant (ANOVA) metabolites in root tissue, a large proportion of amino
331 acids were higher at Station A during cold period (Fig. 5). We found significant negative
332 relationships between leaf glutamate and horizontal rhizome production ($R^2 = -0.45$, Fig. 6),
333 and leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ ($R^2 = -0.43$), this establishes a link between the traditional ecological indicators
334 and metabolomics.

335

336 **Discussion**

337 Traditional seagrass-based indicators and metabolomic analyses revealed that the performance
338 of *C. nodosa* was altered under abiotic stress from aquaculture effluents. The traditional
339 indicators demonstrate higher nutrient loading and lower growth at Station A. Significant
340 elevation of CRS pools and TN in the sediment and pore water ammonium at Station A suggests
341 that the benthos was impacted by effluents from the fish-farm, similar to high sediment TN
342 measured in an organically enriched *C. nodosa* meadow in Crete [0.8 % DW (Apostolaki et
343 al., 2018)]. A comparable two-fold increase in pore-water ammonium with proximity to fish-
344 cages has been found previously in the Mediterranean (Apostolaki et al., 2011). Decrease in
345 root biomass has also been observed elsewhere, due to shading (Martin et al., 2018), salinity
346 increases (Pagès et al., 2010) and effects of fish farming (Delgado et al., 1999), revealing that
347 *C. nodosa* was under stress. Similarly, lower rhizome production at Station A suggests impacts
348 of fish-farm effluent with proximity to the source, comparable to a two-fold reduction in *P.*
349 *oceanica* growth after the installation of fish-cages within 400 m (Marbà et al., 2006). Nutrient
350 availability has been shown to stimulate (Perez et al., 1991), or impair growth (Cunha &
351 Duarte, 2004; Perez et al., 1994) depending on the degree of nutrient enrichment. The fact that
352 the majority of elemental concentrations and isotopic levels in the three seagrass tissues were

353 higher at Station A implies a higher degree of impact from the fish-farm effluent (Marta Pérez
354 et al., 2008), impairing growth. Leaf C and leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ at Station B were similar to the values
355 reported from the Western Mediterranean for *C. nodosa* (Fourqurean et al., 2007), however, at
356 Station A they exceeded these values (leaf C in warm period only), suggesting increased
357 uptake. High growth demands in the summer result in seagrasses N demand exceeding the
358 supply (Pedersen & Borum, 1992). This could explain why we found that N in all tissues
359 followed a seasonal pattern comparable with previous studies, where the higher values were in
360 the cold period not the warm (Fourqurean et al., 1997). Sulfide intrusion was moderate and
361 ranged lower than previously reported (Apostolaki et al., 2018). [20 – 45 %, 25 – 45 %, 20 –
362 50 %, for leaves, rhizomes and roots respectively (Apostolaki et al., 2018)].

363 In accordance with the results of traditional indicators, analysis of the metabolome showed that
364 the meadow at Station A has impaired growth, as seen by the decrease in the sugars sucrose,
365 fructose and myo-inositol at Station A. The storage of carbohydrates in seagrass balances the
366 use of carbon by respiration and growth (Alcoverro et al., 2001). Meadows growing in
367 disturbed areas have been shown to contain lower carbohydrate levels in plant tissue, and lower
368 biomass and productivity (Ruiz & Romero, 2003). Volatile organic compounds such as
369 heptacosane and tetracosane, which were lower at Station A, have been identified as plant
370 growth promoters (Jishma et al., 2017; Tahir et al., 2017). Stigmasterol, catechin and alpha-
371 tocopherol (vitamin E) all also have roles in promoting and regulating plant growth (Dufourc,
372 2008; Rani et al., 2011; Semida et al., 2014). As the majority of these ‘growth metabolites’
373 correlated positively with horizontal rhizome production, this indicates they have a positive
374 association.

375 We found that metabolites known to accumulate under plant stress were high in seagrass at
376 Station A, indicating reduced performance. During abiotic stress in plants, specific metabolites
377 increase due to their signaling or protective roles. The amino acid metabolism is reconfigured

378 under stress, which leads to the accumulation of amino acids such as alanine, by way of the
379 alanine and GABA shunts (Diab & Limami, 2016; Jorge et al., 2016; Rocha et al., 2010).
380 Alanine has been found increased in seagrass under sulfide stress (Hasler-Sheetal et al., 2016).
381 Polyamines regulate plant growth, development and stress responses (Shu et al., 2015). The
382 polyamine putrescine is well known to accumulate in plants under stress (Alet et al., 2011;
383 Cuevas et al., 2008), which corresponds well to our measurements of an increase of two orders
384 of magnitude at Station A. Stress can also lead to depletion of some metabolites, as we have
385 observed with 2-oxoglutaric acid and stearic acid at Station A. Stearic acid, and other fatty
386 acids, have been shown to deplete under temperature stress in terrestrial plants (Liu & Huang,
387 2004). The organic acid 2-oxoglutaric acid has been shown to deplete in the leaves of water
388 stressed soybean plants (Silvente et al., 2012). Despite their unique environment, we could
389 expect seagrasses to have similar stress responses as terrestrial plants as stress response
390 mechanisms are largely conserved throughout the plant kingdom (Akpınar et al., 2012).
391 Ongoing abiotic stress is expected to lead to reduced plant performance, and therefore less
392 growth, which is in accordance with the negative correlations found between ‘stress
393 metabolites’ and horizontal rhizome production.

394 The increase of amino acids in the roots at Station A during the cold period, coinciding with
395 higher pore water ammonium levels, could be explained by increased ammonium assimilation.
396 Rapid entry of ammonium into the cells causes many changes to seagrass physiology including
397 impaired ATP production and photosynthetic electron transport (Alexandre et al., 2018;
398 Villazán et al., 2013). To minimize these effects, seagrasses rapidly assimilate ammonium and
399 convert it into amino acids, which depletes carbon skeletons (Brun et al., 2002, 2008).

400 The GOGAT cycle, where nitrate or ammonium are ultimately integrated into amino acids, is
401 recognised as the most important route of nitrogen assimilation in higher plants (Robinson et
402 al., 1991), of which glutamate is a central metabolite. Glutamate can induce the expression of

403 stress related genes as part of plant stress response (Kan et al., 2017). It has been suggested that
404 regulation of genes in this pathway could be used as an indicator for exposure to ammonium
405 pulses in seagrass (Pernice et al., 2016). Passive ammonium transport is not regulated
406 (Touchette & Burkholder, 2000), therefore uptake of ammonium by the plant continues. The
407 significant negative relationships between leaf glutamate and leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, and horizontal rhizome
408 production indicate the usefulness of glutamate as an indicator for plant stress.

409 Combining metabolomics and traditional indicators provide opportunities to speed up
410 monitoring. Leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ is currently among the most rapid purpose-specific indicators for
411 nutrient stress in small seagrasses, and has a response time of around eight weeks, considerably
412 faster than shoot density (Roca et al., 2016). Metabolomics could allow even earlier detection
413 because metabolites are altered from the moment the plant stress response is activated
414 (Nakabayashi & Saito, 2015). Integrating metabolomics and traditional indicators provides a
415 comprehensive picture that is benefitted by evidence of metabolism response. The pattern of
416 ‘stress’ and ‘growth’ metabolites presented in this study are supported by the observations by
417 the traditional tissue nutrient and biogeochemical indicators; that abiotic stress is increased
418 with proximity to the fish-farm, and therefore *C. nodosa* performance is impaired although it
419 is widely considered a resilient species (Boudouresque et al., 2009). In future research, the
420 metabolism of *C. nodosa* should be studied in more depth. This study would have benefitted
421 from an increased number of sample stations. Yet the results of this study indicate that
422 metabolomic fingerprinting can serve as a reliable early warning indicator and help provide a
423 more thorough picture of plant performance, in particular ‘stress’ or ‘growth’ associated
424 metabolites should be considered when selecting new indicators for seagrass health assessment.

425
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427 **References**

- 428
- 429 Agawin, N. S. R., Duarte, C. M., & Fortes, M. D. (1996). Nutrient limitation of Philippine
- 430 seagrasses (Cape Bolinao, NW Philippines): in situ experimental evidence. *Marine*
- 431 *Ecology Progress Series*, 138, 233–243. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps138233>
- 432 Akpinar, B. A., Avsar, B., Lucas, S. J., & Budak, H. (2012). Plant abiotic stress signaling.
- 433 *Plant Signaling & Behavior*, 7(11), 1450–1455. <https://doi.org/10.4161/psb.21894>
- 434 Alcoverro, T., Manzanera, M., & Romero, J. (2001). Annual metabolic carbon balance of the
- 435 seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: the importance of carbohydrate reserves. *Marine Ecology*
- 436 *Progress Series*, 211, 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps211105>
- 437 Alet, A. I., Sanchez, D. H., Cuevas, J. C., Del Valle, S., Altabella, T., Tiburcio, A. F., Marco,
- 438 F., Ferrando, A., Espasandín, F. D., González, M. E., Ruiz, O. A., & Carrasco, P.
- 439 (2011). Putrescine accumulation in *Arabidopsis thaliana* transgenic lines enhances
- 440 tolerance to dehydration and freezing stress. *Plant Signaling & Behavior*, 6(2), 278–286.
- 441 <https://doi.org/10.4161/PSB.6.2.14702>
- 442 Alexandre, A., Silva, J., & Santos, R. (2018). Light Is More Important Than Nutrient Ratios
- 443 of Fertilization for *Cymodocea nodosa* Seedling Development. *Frontiers in Plant*
- 444 *Science*, 9, 768. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.00768>
- 445 Apostolaki, E. T., Holmer, M., Marbà, N., & Karakassis, I. (2011). Reduced carbon
- 446 sequestration in a Mediterranean seagrass (*Posidonia oceanica*) ecosystem impacted by
- 447 fish farming. *Aquaculture Environmental Interactions*, 2, 49–59.
- 448 <https://doi.org/10.3354/aei00031>
- 449 Apostolaki, E. T., Holmer, M., Santinelli, V., & Karakassis, I. (2018). Species-specific
- 450 response to sulfide intrusion in native and exotic Mediterranean seagrasses under stress.
- 451 *Marine Environmental Research*, 134, 85–95.
- 452 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2017.12.006>

- 453 Bino, R. J., Hall, R. D., Fiehn, O., Kopka, J., Saito, K., Draper, J., Nikolau, B. J., Mendes, P.,
454 Roessner-Tunali, U., Beale, M. H., Trethewey, R. N., Lange, B. M., Wurtele, E. S., &
455 Sumner, L. W. (2004). Potential of metabolomics as a functional genomics tool.
456 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2004.07.004>
- 457 Borum, J., & Greve, T. (2004). *The four European seagrass species. European Seagrasses:*
458 *An Introduction to Monitoring and Management. The M&MS Project.*
- 459 Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Pergent, G., Shili, A., & Verlaque, M. (2009). Regression
460 of Mediterranean seagrasses caused by natural processes and anthropogenic disturbances
461 and stress: a critical review, 52(5), 395–418. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bot.2009.057>
- 462 Brun, F. G., Hernández, I., Vergara, J. J., Peralta, G., & Pérez-Lloréns, J. L. (2002).
463 Assessing the toxicity of ammonium pulses to the survival and growth of *Zostera noltii*.
464 *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 225, 177–187. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps225177>
- 465 Brun, F. G., Olivé, I., Malta, E. J., Vergara, J. J., Hernández, I., & Pérez-Lloréns, J. L.
466 (2008). Increased vulnerability of *Zostera noltii* to stress caused by low light and
467 elevated ammonium levels under phosphate deficiency. *Marine Ecology Progress*
468 *Series*, 365, 67–75. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07512>
- 469 Chong, J., Soufan, O., Li, C., Caraus, I., Li, S., Bourque, G., Wishart, D. S., & Xia, J. (2018).
470 MetaboAnalyst 4.0: towards more transparent and integrative metabolomics analysis.
471 *Nucleic Acids Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky310>
- 472 Christianen, M. J. A., Govers, L. L., Bouma, T. J., Kiswara, W., Roelofs, J. G. M., Lamers, L.
473 P. M., & van Katwijk, M. M. (2012). Marine megaherbivore grazing may increase
474 seagrass tolerance to high nutrient loads. *Journal of Ecology*, 100(2), 546–560.
475 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2745.2011.01900.x>
- 476 Cuevas, J. C., López-Cobollo, R., Alcázar, R., Zarza, X., Koncz, C., Altabella, T., Salinas, J.,
477 Tiburcio, A. F., & Ferrando, A. (2008). Putrescine Is Involved in Arabidopsis Freezing

- 478 Tolerance and Cold Acclimation by Regulating Abscisic Acid Levels in Response to
479 Low Temperature. *Plant Physiology*, 148(2), 1094 LP – 1105.
480 <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.108.122945>
- 481 Cunha, A. H., & Duarte, A. C. M. (2004). Population age structure and rhizome growth of
482 *Cymodocea nodosa* in the Ria Formosa (southern Portugal). *Marine Biology*, 146, 841–
483 847. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-004-1496-2>
- 484 Davey, P. A., Pernice, M., Sablok, G., Larkum, A., Lee, H. T., Golicz, A., Edwards, D.,
485 Dolferus, R., & Ralph, P. (2016). The emergence of molecular profiling and omics
486 techniques in seagrass biology; furthering our understanding of seagrasses. *Functional
487 and Integrative Genomics*, 16(5), 465–480. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10142-016-0501-4>
- 488 Delgado, O., Grau, A., Pou, S., Riera, F., Massuti, C., Ala, M. Z., & Ballesteros, E. (1997).
489 Seagrass regression caused by fish cultures in Fornells Bay (Menorca, Western
490 Mediterranean). *Oceanologica Acta*, 20(3), 557–563.
- 491 Delgado, O., Ruiz, J., Pérez, M., Romero, J., & Ballesteros, E. (1999). Effects of fish farming
492 on seagrass (*Posidonia oceanica*) in a Mediterranean bay: seagrass decline after organic
493 loading cessation. *Oceanologica Acta*, 22(1), 109–117. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0399-
494 1784\(99\)80037-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0399-1784(99)80037-1)
- 495 Diab, H., & Limami, A. M. (2016). Reconfiguration of N Metabolism upon Hypoxia Stress
496 and Recovery: Roles of Alanine Aminotransferase (AlaAT) and Glutamate
497 Dehydrogenase (GDH). *Plants (Basel, Switzerland)*, 5(2), 25.
498 <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants5020025>
- 499 Duarte, C. M., Marba, N., Cebrianl, J., Enriquezl, S., Fortes, M. D., Gallegos, M. E., Merino,
500 M., Olesen, B., Sand-Jensen, K., Uri, J., & Vermaat, J. (1994). Reconstruction of
501 seagrass dynamics: age determinations and associated tools for the seagrass ecologist.
502 *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 107, 195–209. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps107195>

- 503 Dufourc, E. J. (2008). The role of phytosterols in plant adaptation to temperature. *Plant*
504 *Signaling & Behavior*, 3(2), 133–134.
505 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4161/psb.3.2.5051>
- 506 El-Hacen, E.-H. M., Bouma, T. J., Fivash, G. S., Sall, A. A., Piersma, T., Olf, H., & Govers,
507 L. L. (2018). Evidence for ‘critical slowing down’ in seagrass: a stress gradient
508 experiment at the southern limit of its range. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 17263.
509 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-34977-5>
- 510 Exadactylos, A. (2015). Molecular Approach of Seagrasses Response Related to Tolerance
511 Acquisition to Abiotic Stress. In *Molecular Approaches to Genetic Diversity*. InTech.
512 <https://doi.org/10.5772/59425>
- 513 Fiehn, O. (2002). Metabolomics – the link between genotypes and phenotypes. *Plant*
514 *Molecular Biology*, 48(1), 155–171. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013713905833>
- 515 Fourqurean, J. W., Marbà, N., Duarte, C. M., Diaz-Almela, E., & Ruiz-Halpern, S. (2007).
516 Spatial and temporal variation in the elemental and stable isotopic content of the
517 seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa* from the Illes Balears, Spain.
518 *Marine Biology*, 151(1), 219–232. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-006-0473-3>
- 519 Fourqurean, J. W., Moore, T. O., Fry, B., & Hollibaugh, J. T. (1997). Spatial and temporal
520 variation in C:N:P ratios, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of eelgrass *Zostera marina* as indicators of
521 ecosystem processes, Tomales Bay, California, USA. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*,
522 157, 147–157. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps157147>
- 523 Fourqurean, J. W., Zieman, J. C., & Powell, G. V. N. (1992). Relationships between
524 porewater nutrients and seagrasses in a subtropical carbonate environment. *Marine*
525 *Biology*, 114(1), 57–65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00350856>
- 526 Garrido, M., Lafabrie, C., Torre, F., Fernandez, C., & Pasqualini, V. (2013). Resilience and
527 stability of *Cymodocea nodosa* seagrass meadows over the last four decades in a

- 528 Mediterranean lagoon. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 130, 89–98.
529 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2013.05.035>
- 530 Hasler-Sheetal, H., Castorani, M. C. N., Glud, R. N., Canfield, D. E., & Holmer, M. (2016).
531 Metabolomics Reveals Cryptic Interactive Effects of Species Interactions and
532 Environmental Stress on Nitrogen and Sulfur Metabolism in Seagrass.
533 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b04647>
- 534 Hasler-Sheetal, H., Fragner, L., Holmer, M., & Weckwerth, W. (2015). Diurnal effects of
535 anoxia on the metabolome of the seagrass *Zostera marina*. *Metabolomics*, 11(5), 1208–
536 1218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11306-015-0776-9>
- 537 Holmer, M., Argyrou, M., Dalsgaard, T., Danovaro, R., Diaz-Almela, E., Duarte, C. M.,
538 Frederiksen, M., Grau, A., Karakassis, I., Marbà, N., Mirto, S., Pérez, M., Pusceddu, A.,
539 & Tsapakis, M. (2008). Effects of fish farm waste on *Posidonia oceanica* meadows:
540 Synthesis and provision of monitoring and management tools. *Marine Pollution*
541 *Bulletin*, 56(9), 1618–1629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2008.05.020>
- 542 Holmer, M., & Hasler-Sheetal, H. (2014). Sulfide intrusion in seagrasses assessed by stable
543 sulfur isotopes - a synthesis of current results. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 1, 64.
544 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2014.00064>
- 545 Holmer, M., & Kendrick, G. A. (2013). High Sulfide Intrusion in Five Temperate Seagrasses
546 Growing Under Contrasting Sediment Conditions. *Estuaries and Coasts*, 36(1), 116–
547 126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-012-9550-7>
- 548 Horgan, R., Clancy, O., Myers, J., & Baker, P. (2009). An overview of proteomic and
549 metabolomic technologies and their application to pregnancy research. *BJOG: An*
550 *International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 116(2), 173–181.
551 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-0528.2008.01997.x>
- 552 Ibarra-Obando, S. E., Heck, K. L., & Spitzer, P. M. (2004). Effects of simultaneous changes

- 553 in light, nutrients, and herbivory levels, on the structure and function of a subtropical
554 turtlegrass meadow. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 301(2), 193–
555 224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEMBE.2003.10.001>
- 556 IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 25.0. (n.d.). Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.
- 557 Ivancic, I., & Degobbi, D. (1984). An optimal manual procedure for ammonia analysis in
558 natural waters by the Indophenol Blue method. *Water Research*, 8(9), 1–3.
559 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354\(84\)90230-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354(84)90230-6)
- 560 Jiang, Z., Huang, X., & Zhang, J. (2013). Dynamics of nonstructural carbohydrates in
561 seagrass *Thalassia hemprichii* and its response to shading. *Acta Oceanologica Sinica*,
562 32(8), 61–67. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13131-013-0342-0>
- 563 Jishma, P., Hussain, N., Chellappan, R., Rajendran, R., Mathew, J., & Radhakrishnan, E. K.
564 (2017). Strain-specific variation in plant growth promoting volatile organic compounds
565 production by five different *Pseudomonas* spp. as confirmed by response of *Vigna*
566 *radiata* seedlings. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 123(1), 204–216.
567 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.13474>
- 568 Jorge, T. F., Rodrigues, J. A., Caldana, C., Schmidt, R., van Dongen, J. T., Thomas-Oates, J.,
569 & António, C. (2016). Mass spectrometry-based plant metabolomics: Metabolite
570 responses to abiotic stress. *Mass Spectrometry Reviews*, 35(5), 620–649.
571 <https://doi.org/10.1002/mas.21449>
- 572 Kan, C.-C., Chung, T.-Y., Wu, H.-Y., Juo, Y.-A., & Hsieh, M.-H. (2017). Exogenous
573 glutamate rapidly induces the expression of genes involved in metabolism and defense
574 responses in rice roots. *BMC Genomics*, 18(1), 186. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-017-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-017-3588-7)
575 [3588-7](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-017-3588-7)
- 576 Kletou, D., Kleitou, P., Savva, I., Attrill, M. J., Antoniou, C., & Hall-Spencer, J. M. (2018).
577 Seagrass recovery after fish farm relocation in the eastern Mediterranean. *Marine*

- 578 *Environmental Research*, 140, 221–233.
579 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2018.06.007>
- 580 Kumar, M., Kuzhiumparambil, U., Pernice, M., Jiang, Z., & Ralph, P. J. (2016).
581 Metabolomics: an emerging frontier of systems biology in marine macrophytes. *Algal*
582 *Research*, 16, 76–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2016.02.033>
- 583 Liu, X., & Huang, B. (2004). *Changes in Fatty Acid Composition and Saturation in Leaves*
584 *and Roots of Creeping Bentgrass Exposed to High Soil Temperature*. *Journal of the*
585 *American Society for Horticultural Science* (Vol. 129).
586 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.129.6.0795>
- 587 Macreadie, P. I., Schliep, M. T., Rasheed, M. A., Chartrand, K. M., & Ralph, P. J. (2014).
588 Molecular indicators of chronic seagrass stress: A new era in the management of
589 seagrass ecosystems? *Ecological Indicators*, 38, 279–281.
590 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLIND.2013.11.017>
- 591 Malandrakis, E. E., Danis, T., Iona, A., & Exadactylos, A. (2017a). Abiotic Stress of
592 Seagrasses: Recent Advances in Transcriptomics, Genomics, and Systems Biology. In
593 *Systems Biology of Marine Ecosystems* (pp. 119–132). Cham: Springer International
594 Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-62094-7_6
- 595 Malandrakis, E. E., Dadali, O., Kavouras, M., Danis, T., Panagiotaki, P., Miliou, H., Tsioli,
596 S., Orfanidis, S., Küpper, F. C., & Exadactylos, A. (2017b). Identification of the abiotic
597 stress-related transcription in little Neptune grass *Cymodocea nodosa* with RNA-seq.
598 *Marine Genomics*, 34, 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margen.2017.03.005>
- 599 Marbà, N., Krause-Jensen, D., Alcoverro, T., Birk, S., Pedersen, A., Neto, J. M., Orfanidis,
600 S., Garmendia, J. M., Muxika, I., Borja, A., Dencheva, K., & Duarte, C. M. (2013).
601 Diversity of European seagrass indicators: Patterns within and across regions.
602 *Hydrobiologia*, 704(1), 265–278. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-012-1403-7>

- 603 Marbà, N., Santiago, R., Díaz-Almela, E., Álvarez, E., & Duarte, C. M. (2006). Seagrass
604 (*Posidonia oceanica*) vertical growth as an early indicator of fish farm-derived stress.
605 *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 67(3), 475–483.
606 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2005.11.034>
- 607 Martin, B. C., Statton, J., Siebers, A. R., Grierson, P. F., Ryan, M. H., & Kendrick, G. A.
608 (2018). Colonizing tropical seagrasses increase root exudation under fluctuating and
609 continuous low light. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 63(S1), S381–S391.
610 <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.10746>
- 611 Meyer, R. C., Steinfath, M., Liseč, J., Becher, M., Witucka-Wall, H., Törjék, O., Fiehn, O.,
612 Eckardt, A., Willmitzer, L., Selbig, J., & Altmann, T. (2007). The metabolic signature
613 related to high plant growth rate in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Proceedings of the National*
614 *Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 104(11), 4759–4764.
615 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0609709104>
- 616 Mishra, A., Cabaço, S., Vizzini, S., Santos, R., & Apostolaki, E. (2018). *Population dynamics*
617 *of Cymodocea nodosa in the vicinity of volcanic CO2 seeps*.
- 618 Nakabayashi, R., & Saito, K. (2015). Integrated metabolomics for abiotic stress responses in
619 plants. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology*, 24, 10–16.
620 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.PBI.2015.01.003>
- 621 Obata, T., Witt, S., Liseč, J., Palacios-Rojas, N., Florez-Sarasa, I., Yousfi, S., Araus, J. L.,
622 Cairns, J. E., & Fernie, A. R. (2015). Metabolite Profiles of Maize Leaves in Drought,
623 Heat, and Combined Stress Field Trials Reveal the Relationship between Metabolism
624 and Grain Yield. *Plant Physiology*, 169(4), 2665–2683.
625 <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.15.01164>
- 626 Orlando-Bonaca, M., Lipej, L., & Francé, J. (2016). The most suitable time and depth to
627 sample *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Ascherson meadows in the shallow coastal area.

- 628 Experiences from the northern Adriatic Sea. *Acta Adriatica*, 57(2), 251–262.
- 629 Orth, R. J., Carruthers, T. J. B., Dennison, W. C., Duarte, C. M., Fourqurean, J. W., Heck, K.
630 L., Hughes, A. R., Kendrick, G. A., Kenworthy, W. J., Olyarnik, S., Short, F. T.,
631 Waycott, M., & Williams, S. L. (2006). A Global Crisis for Seagrass Ecosystems.
632 *BioScience*, 56(12), 987–996. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2006)56[987:agcfse]2.0.co;2)
633 [3568\(2006\)56\[987:agcfse\]2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2006)56[987:agcfse]2.0.co;2)
- 634 Pagès, J. F., Pérez, M., & Romero, J. (2010). Sensitivity of the seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa*
635 to hypersaline conditions: A microcosm approach. *Journal of Experimental Marine*
636 *Biology and Ecology*, 386(1–2), 34–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEMBE.2010.02.017>
- 637 Papathanasiou, V., Orfanidis, S., & Brown, M. T. (2016). *Cymodocea nodosa* metrics as
638 bioindicators of anthropogenic stress in N. Aegean, Greek coastal waters. *Ecological*
639 *Indicators*, 63, 61–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.11.059>
- 640 Pedersen, M. F., & Borum, J. (1992). Nitrogen dynamics of eelgrass *Zostera marina* during a
641 late summer period of high growth and low nutrient availability. *Marine Ecology*
642 *Progress Series*, 80, 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps080065>
- 643 Peng, B., Li, H., & Peng, X.-X. (2015). Functional metabolomics: from biomarker discovery
644 to metabolome reprogramming. *Protein & Cell*, 6(9), 628–637.
645 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13238-015-0185-x>
- 646 Pérez, M., Duarte, C. M., Romero, J., Sand-Jensen, K., & Alcoverro, T. (1994). Growth
647 plasticity in *Cymodocea nodosa* stands: the importance of nutrient supply. *Aquatic*
648 *Botany*, 47(3–4), 249–264. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3770\(94\)90056-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3770(94)90056-6)
- 649 Pérez, M., Romero, J., Duarte, C. M., & Sand-Jensen, K. (1991). Phosphorus limitation of
650 *Cymodocea nodosa* growth. *Marine Biology*, 109(1), 129–133.
651 <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01320239>
- 652 Pérez, Marta, García, T., Invers, O., & Ruiz, J. M. (2008). Physiological responses of the

- 653 seagrass *Posidonia oceanica* as indicators of fish farm impact. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*,
654 56(5), 869–879. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2008.02.001>
- 655 Pernice, M., Sinutok, S., Sablok, G., Commault, A. S., Schliep, M., Macreadie, P. I.,
656 Rasheed, M. A., & Ralph, P. J. (2016). Molecular physiology reveals ammonium uptake
657 and related gene expression in the seagrass *Zostera muelleri*. *Marine Environmental*
658 *Research*, 122, 126–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARENRES.2016.10.003>
- 659 Piro, A., Marín-Guirao, L., Serra, I. A., Spadafora, A., Sandoval-Gil, J. M., Bernardeau-
660 Esteller, J., Fernandez, J. M. R., & Mazzuca, S. (2015). The modulation of leaf
661 metabolism plays a role in salt tolerance of *Cymodocea nodosa* exposed to hypersaline
662 stress in mesocosms. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 6, 464.
663 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2015.00464>
- 664 R: A language and environment for statistical computing. (2013). R Foundation for Statistical
665 Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- 666 Rani, A., Kumar Vats, S., Sharma, M., & Kumar, S. (2011). Catechin promotes growth of
667 *Arabidopsis thaliana* with concomitant changes in vascular system, photosynthesis and
668 hormone content. *Biologia Plantarum*, 55(4), 779–782. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10535-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10535-011-0187-3)
669 [011-0187-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10535-011-0187-3)
- 670 Robinson, S. A., Slade, A. P., Fox, G. G., Phillips, R., Ratcliffe, R. G., & Stewart, G. R.
671 (1991). The Role of Glutamate Dehydrogenase in Plant Nitrogen Metabolism. *Plant*
672 *Physiology*, 95, 509–516. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.95.2.509>
- 673 Roca, G., Alcoverro, T., Krause-Jensen, D., Balsby, T. J. S., van Katwijk, M. M., Marbà, N.,
674 Santos, R., Arthur, R., Mascaró, O., Fernández-Torquemada, Y., Pérez, M., Duarte, C.
675 M., & Romero, J. (2016). Response of seagrass indicators to shifts in environmental
676 stressors: A global review and management synthesis. *Ecological Indicators*, 63, 310–
677 323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.12.007>

- 678 Rocha, M., Licausi, F., Araújo, W. L., Nunes-Nesi, A., Sodek, L., Fernie, A. R., & van
679 Dongen, J. T. (2010). Glycolysis and the tricarboxylic acid cycle are linked by alanine
680 aminotransferase during hypoxia induced by waterlogging of *Lotus japonicus*. *Plant*
681 *Physiology*, 152(3), 1501–1513. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.109.150045>
- 682 Ruiz, J. M., & Romero, J. (2003). Effects of disturbances caused by coastal constructions on
683 spatial structure, growth dynamics and photosynthesis of the seagrass *Posidonia*
684 *oceanica*. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 46(12), 1523–1533.
685 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2003.08.021>
- 686 Sarà, G, Scilipoti, D., Milazzo, M., & Modica, A. (2006). Use of stable isotopes to investigate
687 dispersal of waste from fish farms as a function of hydrodynamics. *Marine Ecology*
688 *Progress Series*, 313, 261–270. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps313261>
- 689 Sarà, Gianluca. (2007). Ecological effects of aquaculture on living and non-living suspended
690 fractions of the water column: A meta-analysis. *Water Research*, 41(15), 3187–3200.
691 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WATRES.2007.05.013>
- 692 Semida, W. M., Taha, R. S., Abdelhamid, M. T., & Rady, M. M. (2014). Foliar-applied α -
693 tocopherol enhances salt-tolerance in *Vicia faba* L. plants grown under saline conditions.
694 *South African Journal of Botany*, 95, 24–31.
695 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SAJB.2014.08.005>
- 696 Shu, S., Yuan, Y., Chen, J., Sun, J., Zhang, W., Tang, Y., Zhong, M., & Guo, S. (2015). The
697 role of putrescine in the regulation of proteins and fatty acids of thylakoid membranes
698 under salt stress. *Scientific Reports*, 5(1), 14390. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep14390>
- 699 Silvente, S., Sobolev, A. P., & Lara, M. (2012). Metabolite adjustments in drought tolerant
700 and sensitive soybean genotypes in response to water stress. *PloS One*, 7(6), e38554.
701 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0038554>
- 702 Steinberg, C. (2011). *Stress ecology : environmental stress as ecological driving force and*

- 703 *key player in evolution*. Springer.
- 704 Strickland, J. D. H., & Parsons, T. R. (1972). A Practical Handbook of Seawater Analysis.
- 705 *Fisheries Research Board of Canada Bulletin*, 167.
- 706 Tahir, H. A. S., Gu, Q., Wu, H., Raza, W., Hanif, A., Wu, L., Colman, M. V., & Gao, X.
- 707 (2017). Plant Growth Promotion by Volatile Organic Compounds Produced by *Bacillus*
- 708 *subtilis* SYST2. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 8, 171.
- 709 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00171>
- 710 The Arabidopsis Genome Initiative. (2000). Analysis of the genome sequence of the
- 711 flowering plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Nature*, 408, 796.
- 712 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/35048692>
- 713 Touchette, B. W., & Burkholder, J. M. (2000). *Review of nitrogen and phosphorus*
- 714 *metabolism in seagrasses*. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* (Vol.
- 715 250). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981\(00\)00195-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981(00)00195-7)
- 716 Tsagaraki, T., Petihakis, G., Tsiaras, K., Triantafyllou, G., Tsapakis, M., Korres, G.,
- 717 Kakagiannis, G., Frangoulis, C., & Karakassis, I. (2011). Beyond the cage: Ecosystem
- 718 modelling for impact evaluation in aquaculture. *Ecological Modelling*, 222(14), 2512–
- 719 2523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLMODEL.2010.11.027>
- 720 Tsagaraki, T., Pitta, P., Frangoulis, C., Petihakis, G., & Karakassis, I. (2013). Plankton
- 721 response to nutrient enrichment is maximized at intermediate distances from fish farms.
- 722 *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 493, 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10520>
- 723 Tutar, O., Marín-Guirao, L., Ruiz, J. M., & Procaccini, G. (2017). Antioxidant response to
- 724 heat stress in seagrasses. A gene expression study. *Marine Environmental Research*,
- 725 132, 94–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARENRES.2017.10.011>
- 726 Urbanczyk-Wochniak, E., Luedemann, A., Kopka, J., Selbig, J., Roessner-Tunali, U.,
- 727 Willmitzer, L., & Fernie, A. R. (2003). Parallel analysis of transcript and metabolic

- 728 profiles: a new approach in systems biology. *EMBO Reports*, 4(10), 989–993.
729 <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.embor.embor944>
- 730 van Katwijk, M. M., van der Welle, M. E. W., Lucassen, E. C. H. E. T., Vonk, J. A.,
731 Christianen, M. J. A., Kiswara, W., Inayat al Hakim, I., Arifin, A., Bouma, T. J.,
732 Roelofs, J. G. M., & Lamers, L. P. M. (2011). Early warning indicators for river nutrient
733 and sediment loads in tropical seagrass beds: A benchmark from a near-pristine
734 archipelago in Indonesia. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 62(7), 1512–1520.
735 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2011.04.007>
- 736 Villazán, B., Brun, F. G., Jiménez-Ramos, R., Pérez-Lloréns, J. L., & Vergara, J. J. (2013).
737 Interaction between ammonium and phosphate uptake rates in the seagrass *Zostera*
738 *noltii*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 488, 133–143.
739 <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10395>
- 740

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748

749 **Declarations of interest:** none

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752 **Figure Legends**

753 Fig. 1. Map of sampling area in the Argolikos Gulf with stations A and B indicated. Fish farm
754 cages are indicated by circles.

755

756 Fig. 2. Scores plots of PCA analyses of metabolite relative concentrations in *C. nodosa* leaves
757 at the two sites, in two seasons.

758

759 Fig. 3. Heatmaps of metabolites in leaf tissue showing: (Left) plant growth associated
760 metabolites, and (Right) Stress related metabolites in plants.

761

762 Fig. 4. Linear regressions between horizontal rhizome production and (Top) Sucrose and
763 (Bottom) L-alanine.

764

765 Fig. 5. Heatmap of the 20 most significantly different root metabolites between station or
766 sample site (2-way ANOVA).

767

768 Fig. 6. Linear regressions of (Top) Horizontal rhizome production and leaf glutamate, (Middle)
769 Pore water ammonium and leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and (Bottom) Leaf glutamate and leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$.

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773 **Figure 1.**

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777 **Figure 2.**

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781 **Figure 3.**

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787 **Figure 5.**

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791 **Figure 6.**

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793 **Table Legends**

794 Table 1. Ammonium, phosphate and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ sulfate of bottom water and pore water for each
795 station. Organic (OC) and inorganic (IC) carbon and total nitrogen (TN) pools and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ sulfide
796 of seagrass sediments. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between stations are given by capital
797 letters and between season by small letters, * indicates station X season effect.

798

799 Table 2. Shoot density, leaf, rhizome and root biomass, above to below ground biomass ratio,
800 total biomass and horizontal rhizome production, and average TC, TN, TS, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$,
801 $F_{\text{sulfide AVS}}$ and $F_{\text{sulfide CRS}}$ for leaves rhizomes and roots at the two stations during the warm
802 and cold periods. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between stations are given by capital letters
803 (A) and between seasons by small letters (a), * indicates station X season effect.

804

805 Table 3. Two-way ANOVA testing of stress-associated and growth-associated metabolites in
806 seagrass leaves.

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808 Table 4. Spearman correlations between horizontal rhizome production and metabolites
809 associated with growth or stress in seagrass leaves in both sampling periods.

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818 **Table 1.**

	Station A		Station B	
	Warm Period	Cold Period	Warm Period	Cold Period
<i>Bottom water</i>				
NH ₄ (μM)	0.45 ± 0.10	0.99 ± 0.55	0.40 ± 0.09	0.54 ± 0.10
PO ₄ (μM)	0.02 ± 0.01 a	0.07 ± 0.06 a	0.01 ± 0.006 a	0.05 ± 0.03 a
δ ³⁴ S sulfate (‰)	20.71	20.69	20.28	20.70
POC (μg/L)	153.40 ± 5.37	301.29 ± 323.33	139.23 ± 67.07	100.29 ± 76.73
PN (μg/L)	50.10 ± 5.02	20.02 ± 16.19	16.18 ± 15.10	11.71 ± 10.34
<i>Pore water</i>				
NH ₄ (μM)	2.74 ± 0.85 A	6.07 ± 2.13 A	2.48 ± 0.36 A	2.46 ± 1.08 A
PO ₄ (μM)	0.73 ± 0.30 a	0.18 ± 0.04 a	0.47 ± 0.11 a	0.275 ± 0.03 a
δ ³⁴ S sulfate (‰)	20.58 ± 0.06	20.53 ± 0.20	20.41 ± 0.14	19.91 ± 1.06
<i>Sediment</i>				
OC (% DW)	6.25 ± 0.42 a	3.51 ± 0.12 a	5.99 ± 0.76 a	3.36 ± 0.08 a
IC (% DW)	3.75 ± 0.19 a	6.78 ± 0.23 a	3.98 ± 0.86 a	6.36 ± 0.79 a
TN (% DW)	0.074 ± 0.01 Aa	0.061 ± 0.003 Aa	0.05 ± 0.006 Aa	0.05 ± 0.0009 Aa
δ ¹³ C (‰)	-0.85 ± 0.69 a*	-1.66 ± 0.58 a*	0.43 ± 0.23 a*	-1.84 ± 0.73 a*
δ ¹⁵ N (‰)	0.66 ± 0.35 a	1.49 ± 0.15 a	0.77 ± 0.19 a	1.81 ± 0.48 a
δ ³⁴ S sulfide (AVS pools) (‰)	-19.92 ± 1.64	-17.82 ± 3.26	-20.11 ± 1.49	-18.27 ± 6.85
δ ³⁴ S sulfide (CRS pools) (‰)	-26.81 ± 0.60	-25.26 ± 1.27	-27.46 ± 0.58	-27.67 ± 1.51
S AVS pools (μM)	155.75 ± 45.17 *	55.28 ± 41.90 *	110.98 ± 43.17 *	185.87 ± 50.57 *
S CRS pools (μM)	11686.35 ± 1051.82 A	8813.33 ± 5381.55 A	4465.4 ± 713.35 A	7413.33 ± 1250.34 A

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821 **Table 2.**

	Station A		Station B	
	Warm Period	Cold Period	Warm Period	Cold Period
Shoot density (shoots m ⁻²)	2569.19 ± 185.97 a	1032.77 ± 297.21 a	1822.20 ± 967.34 a	1369.48 ± 374.09 a
Leaf biomass (g DW m ⁻²)	37.50 ± 4.16 a	10.33 ± 2.74 a	36.75 ± 19.48 a	13.00 ± 1.89 a
Rhizome biomass (g DW m ⁻²)	113.83 ± 46.38*	46.22 ± 12.48*	78.05 ± 22.60*	93.85 ± 33.41*
Root biomass (g DW m ⁻²)	33.86 ± 8.70 A	25.00 ± 6.71 A	48.37 ± 26.20 A	69.31 ± 40.80 A
Above:Below-ground biomass	0.21 ± 0.05 a	0.13 ± 0.01 a	0.21 ± 0.06 a	0.08 ± 0.04 a
Total biomass (g DW m ⁻²)	185.19 ± 46.00 a	56.55 ± 14.95 a	163.17 ± 62.17 a	106.84 ± 34.99 a
Horizontal rhizome production (g m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)	0.67 ± 0.54 A		1.57 ± 0.78 A	
Leaf C (% DW)	41.07 ± 0.21 Aa	37.79 ± 1.64 Aa	39.84 ± 2.95 Aa	37.86 ± 0.56 Aa
Rhizome C (% DW)	38.50 ± 1.57 Aa	36.56 ± 1.51 Aa	39.92 ± 0.84 Aa	37.69 ± 0.86 Aa
Root C (% DW)	40.69 ± 0.70 a	37.26 ± 0.85 a	40.08 ± 0.83 a	37.51 ± 1.19 a
Leaf N (% DW)	1.81 ± 0.12 a	2.22 ± 0.45 a	1.73 ± 0.33 a	2.29 ± 0.11 a
Rhizome N (% DW)	0.69 ± 0.05 Aa	1.80 ± 0.25 Aa	0.52 ± 0.15 Aa	1.43 ± 0.15 Aa
Root N (% DW)	0.76 ± 0.10 Aa	1.09 ± 0.07 Aa	0.52 ± 0.15 Aa	0.83 ± 0.09 Aa
Leaf S (% DW)	0.39 ± 0.03 A*	0.31 ± 0.04 A*	0.34 ± 0.03 A*	0.39 ± 0.04 A*
Rhizome S (% DW)	0.45 ± 0.04 A*	0.38 ± 0.10 A*	0.35 ± 0.06 A*	0.41 ± 0.04 A*
Root S (% DW)	0.48 ± 0.08 A	0.42 ± 0.13 A	0.34 ± 0.04 A	0.35 ± 0.05 A
Leaf δ ¹³ C (‰)	-7.69 ± 0.25 A	-6.24 ± 3.86 A	-8.16 ± 0.22 A	-7.53 ± 0.16 A
Rhizome δ ¹³ C (‰)	-7.87 ± 0.44 A	-7.83 ± 0.26 A	-8.09 ± 0.08 A	-7.99 ± 0.28 A
Root δ ¹³ C (‰)	-8.22 ± 0.41 A	-8.34 ± 0.36 A	-8.36 ± 0.53 A	-8.41 ± 0.28 A
Leaf δ ¹⁵ N (‰)	2.05 ± 0.51 Aa*	-0.93 ± 0.99 Aa*	1.97 ± 0.43 Aa*	3.34 ± 0.35 Aa*
Rhizome δ ¹⁵ N (‰)	1.14 ± 0.64 a*	-0.31 ± 1.08 a*	-0.19 ± 1.11 a*	3.02 ± 0.23 a*
Root δ ¹⁵ N (‰)	1.92 ± 0.66 A*	0.13 ± 1.03 A*	0.96 ± 0.93 A*	3.51 ± 0.48 A*
Leaf δ ³⁴ S (‰)	16.79 ± 0.28 Aa	15.33 ± 0.74 Aa	16.27 ± 0.64 Aa	15.55 ± 0.89 Aa
Rhizome δ ³⁴ S (‰)	10.17 ± 1.76 A*	8.03 ± 0.49 A*	9.37 ± 1.79 A*	10.57 ± 1.53 A*
Root δ ³⁴ S (‰)	10.55 ± 2.57 A	11.69 ± 1.50 A	11.99 ± 2.63 A	9.64 ± 2.79 A
Leaf F _{sulfide} AVS (%)	9.51 ± 1.13	14.96 ± 0.70	9.77 ± 1.67	13.07 ± 1.82
Rhizome F _{sulfide} AVS (%)	25.41 ± 5.20	32.85 ± 1.46	26.87 ± 3.77	28.10 ± 5.45
Root F _{sulfide} AVS (%)	23.84 ± 9.60	27.10 ± 1.60	16.41 ± 1.97	30.80 ± 5.80
Leaf F _{sulfide} CRS (%)	8.11 ± 0.63	11.43 ± 2.01	8.30 ± 1.73	10.37 ± 0.83
Rhizome F _{sulfide} CRS (%)	21.63 ± 3.64	27.36 ± 0.05	22.80 ± 3.93	22.28 ± 3.69
Root F _{sulfide} CRS (%)	20.18 ± 7.26	20.54 ± 3.53	13.89 ± 1.73	24.76 ± 6.58

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825 **Table 3**

Metabolite	two-way ANOVA test					Metabolite	two-way ANOVA test				
	Source of variability	df	MS	F	p-value		Source of variability	df	MS	F	p-value
<i>Stress Associated</i>						<i>Growth Associated</i>					
L-alanine	Station	1	7.546	10.824	**	Sucrose	Station	1	17.200	170.386	***
	Season	1	0.057	0.081	ns		Season	1	0.115	1.139	ns
	Station x Season	1	0.244	0.349	ns		Station x Season	1	0.070	0.692	ns
L-serine	Station	1	8.710	14.143	**	Fructose	Station	1	16.476	114.642	***
	Season	1	0.316	0.513	ns		Season	1	0.141	0.984	ns
	Station x Season	1	0.120	0.195	ns		Station x Season	1	0.083	0.576	ns
L-proline	Station	1	9.529	16.243	***	myo-Inositol	Station	1	15.399	69.854	***
	Season	1	0.039	0.067	ns		Season	1	0.073	0.331	ns
	Station x Season	1	0.045	0.077	ns		Station x Season	1	0.001	0.005	ns
Putrescine	Station	1	12.405	34.869	***	Heptacosane	Station	1	17.765	260.750	***
	Season	1	0.885	2.486	ns		Season	1	0.072	1.052	ns
	Station x Season	1	0.018	0.051	ns		Station x Season	1	0.074	1.082	ns
L-ornithine	Station	1	13.188	37.759	***	Tetracosane	Station	1	16.851	135.093	***
	Season	1	0.205	0.587	ns		Season	1	0.001	0.009	ns
	Station x Season	1	0.018	0.051	ns		Station x Season	1	0.152	1.219	ns
3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid	Station	1	11.007	34.301	***	Stigmasterol	Station	1	18.081	315.980	***
	Season	1	1.472	4.588	*		Season	1	0.002	0.040	ns
	Station x Season	1	1.386	4.319	ns		Station x Season	1	0.001	0.013	ns
Cinnamic acid	Station	1	14.593	53.525	***	Catechin	Station	1	14.677	58.787	***
	Season	1	0.004	0.016	ns		Season	1	0.283	1.132	ns
	Station x Season	1	0.041	0.149	ns		Station x Season	1	0.046	0.185	ns
2-oxoglutaric acid	Station	1	16.179	91.875	***	alpha-Tocophereol	Station	1	14.357	50.831	***
	Season	1	0.002	0.010	ns		Season	1	0.027	0.096	ns
	Station x Season	1	0.002	0.010	ns		Station x Season	1	0.098	0.345	ns
Stearic acid	Station	1	15.699	107.759	***						
	Season	1	0.346	2.372	ns						
	Station x Season	1	0.624	4.286	ns						

ns not significant

* p < 0.05.

** p < 0.01.

*** p < 0.001.

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828 **Table 4**

Metabolites correlated with horizontal rhizome production	N	Spearman's rho Correlation coefficient	Sig. (1-tailed)	Sig. (2-tailed)
<i>Growth</i>				
Sucrose	20	0.453	*	*
Fructose	20	0.577	**	**
myo-Inositol	20	0.647	**	**
Heptacosane	20	0.620	**	**
Tetracosane	20	0.368	ns	ns
Stigmasterol	20	0.562	**	**
Catechin	20	0.289	ns	ns
alpha-Tocophereol	20	0.525	**	*
<i>Stress</i>				
L-alanine	20	-0.460	*	*
L-serine	20	-0.439	*	ns
L-proline	20	-0.316	ns	ns
Putrescine	20	-0.624	**	**
L-ornithine	20	-0.412	*	ns
3,4-Dihydroxybenzoic acid	20	-0.430	*	ns
Cinnamic acid	20	-0.400	*	ns
2-Oxoglutaric acid	20	0.510	*	*
Stearic acid	20	0.071	ns	ns

ns not significant

* p < 0.05.

** p < 0.01.

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